

Some Problems of Material Engineering of Resin Concretes

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ABSTRACT

Concrete made with portland cement has been the most popular building and construction material in the world for the past 150 years. In fact the cement concrete has been one of the older composite material. However, cement concrete has some disadvantages, such as delayed hardening, low tensile strength, porous structure and poor chemical resistance and so on.

Growing industrial activities create a continual demand for materials that satisfy more stringent requirements. One of those type new building materials have been concretes containing polymers. In the last 20 years we have observed worldwide development of resin concretes.

Generally from the practical point of view high strength and good or even very good chemical resistance have been determined the resin concretes as the building materials. However the most fruitful advantage of resin concrete has been the wide "elasticity" in the sense of material engineering viz. the possibility of producing of material with control properties. The paper deals with this problem.

The model of resin concretes as the composite-like materials, the resin concrete classification and the meaning of resin binder and aggregate have been studied on the base of resin concrete definition. The microstructure of resin concrete as well as their effect on resin concrete properties have been also discussed. The main structure factors expressed by the content of pores in resin concretes as well as the ratio of structural orientation of resin binder and relation between those factors and resin concrete properties has been emphasized. Some practical implications of assume resin concrete structure conception has been also described. The presented way of resin concrete structure understanding can be used to explain some experimental dates as well as it should be useful in searching of new material solutions in range of resin concretes. The existing and potential resin concrete applications have been summarized. The presented review paper has been prepared on the base of world literature including Polish and Japanese publications as well as own studies and practical researches.

